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Abomasal infusion of different exogenous emulsifiers alters fatty acid digestibility and milk fat yield of lactating dairy cows

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Abomasal infusion of different exogenous emulsifiers alters fatty acid digestibility and milk fat yield of lactating dairy cows. *By Prom et al., page XXX.* We evaluated the effects of abomasal infusion of emulsifiers on fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. All emulsifiers examined were polysorbates, nonionic surfactants, consisting of a polyethoxylated sorbitan esterified with fatty acids. Treatments were abomasal infusions of water only or 30 g/d of different emulsifiers: polysorbate-C16:0, polysorbate-C18:0+C16:0, and polysorbate-C18:1. In conclusion, only polysorbate-C18:1 increased the digestibility of total fatty acids. This suggests that the predominant fatty acid present in the polysorbate impacts its ability to improve fatty acid digestibility.

Supplemental Table S1. Milk fatty acid (FA) yields of cows infused with treatments (n = 8)

Variable	Treatments ¹				SEM	P-value ²
	CON	T40	T60	T80		
Selected Individual FA ³ , g/d FA						
C4:0	32.0 ^b	37.6 ^a	35.2 ^{ab}	38.1 ^a	2.71	0.04
C6:0	24.4 ^b	28.3 ^a	26.5 ^{ab}	27.5 ^a	2.31	0.04
C8:0	15.1 ^b	17.5 ^a	16.3 ^a	16.9 ^a	1.45	0.02
C10:0	42.8 ^c	49.6 ^a	46.0 ^{bc}	47.7 ^{ab}	3.77	0.02
C12:0	52.0 ^c	59.9 ^a	55.7 ^{bc}	57.9 ^{ab}	3.97	0.02
C14:0	183 ^b	209 ^a	196 ^{ab}	210 ^a	11.1	0.02
C14:1	11.6	13.4	12.4	12.9	0.97	0.21
C16:0	520 ^c	587 ^a	540 ^{bc}	574 ^{ab}	52.9	0.06
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	21.6	24.3	22.5	23.6	1.60	0.24
C18:0	126 ^b	138 ^{ab}	133 ^{ab}	155 ^a	13.7	0.09
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	2.60 ^b	3.03 ^a	2.73 ^b	3.39 ^a	0.15	0.03
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	2.34 ^b	2.61 ^b	2.46 ^b	3.01 ^a	0.12	0.03
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	5.62	7.18	6.15	8.41	1.61	0.49
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	5.49 ^b	6.37 ^{ab}	5.85 ^b	7.27 ^a	0.31	0.04
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	236 ^c	254 ^b	249 ^b	271 ^a	11.2	0.01
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	6.76	7.23	6.95	7.41	0.40	0.49
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	23.4 ^b	25.8 ^a	23.8 ^b	27.1 ^a	0.57	0.00
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	2.90 ^c	3.58 ^a	3.02 ^{bc}	3.34 ^{ab}	0.17	0.02
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	4.30 ^b	4.72 ^a	4.42 ^b	5.00 ^a	0.14	0.01

^{a-d} For the effect of treatment, means in a row with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$). Separation conducted only if treatment effect was $P < 0.10$.

¹ Treatments were: CON = no emulsifier infusion (water only); T40 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C16:0; T60 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:0+C16:0; T80 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1.

² P-values refer to the effect of treatment.

³ Approximately 80 individual fatty acids were quantified. Only select fatty acids are reported in the table.

Supplemental Table S2. Milk fatty acid (FA) contents of cows infused with treatments (n = 8)

Variable	Treatments ¹				SEM	<i>P</i> -value ²
	CON	T40	T60	T80		
Selected Individual FA ³ , g/100 g FA						
C4:0	2.41	2.37	2.41	2.52	0.06	0.49
C6:0	1.84	1.81	1.80	1.83	0.08	0.92
C8:0	1.13	1.12	1.11	1.13	0.05	0.89
C10:0	3.23	3.19	3.12	3.18	0.12	0.80
C12:0	3.91	3.88	3.79	3.85	0.10	0.62
C14:0	13.8	13.7	13.5	13.9	0.28	0.48
C14:1	0.86	0.88	0.86	0.87	0.04	0.97
C16:0	37.1 ^a	37.5 ^a	36.9 ^a	35.9 ^b	0.87	0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.55	1.60	1.57	1.52	0.07	0.84
C18:0	8.98	8.78	9.12	9.27	0.59	0.62
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.02	0.36
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.20	0.01	0.48
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.42	0.49	0.48	0.60	0.16	0.72
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.40	0.42	0.42	0.48	0.05	0.44
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	17.0	16.4	17.5	17.2	0.76	0.22
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	0.49	0.48	0.50	0.48	0.05	0.93
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	1.70	1.70	1.69	1.75	0.11	0.62
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	0.21	0.25	0.22	0.23	0.03	0.22
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.32	0.02	0.79

^{a-d} For the effect of treatment, means in a row with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

¹ Treatments were: CON = no emulsifier infusion (water only); T40 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C16:0; T60 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:0+C16:0; T80 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1.

² *P*-values refer to the effect of treatment.

³ Approximately 80 individual fatty acids were quantified. Only select fatty acids are reported in the table.

Supplemental Table S3. Plasma nonesterified fatty acids (NEFA), insulin, and glucose of cows infused with treatments (n = 8)

Variable	Treatments ¹				SEM	<i>P</i> -value ²
	CON	T40	T60	T80		
NEFA, mEq/L	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.01	0.13
Insulin, μ g/L	0.51	0.48	0.56	0.51	0.04	0.21
Glucose, μ g/L	65.4	66.1	66.0	64.8	1.05	0.67

^{a-d} For the effect of treatment, means in a row with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

¹ Treatments were: CON = no emulsifier infusion (water only); T40 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C16:0; T60 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:0+C16:0; T80 = infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1.

² *P*-values refer to the effect of treatment.